

Industry 5.0 Concepts and Enabling Technologies, Towards an Enhanced Conservation Practice: Systematic Literature Review Protocol Checklist

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Experienced Researcher: Dr. Alejandro Jiménez Rios

Main Supervisor: Prof. Vagelis Plevris

Secondment Supervisor: Prof. Maria Nogal

Collaborators: Dr. Rafael Ramirez and Margarita L. Petrou

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1 Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review (PRISMA) 2020

1.1 Introduction

A transparent systematic review should present completely and accurately why it has been done, what has been done and what was found. The benefits of a systematic review are:

- They allow to identify future research priorities based on the synthesis of state-of-the-art knowledge in a certain field.
- Questions that cannot be addressed by individual studies can be answered by systematic reviews.
- Give a hint to future studies to rectify aspects of primary research identified on them.
- Provide answers to how and why a particular phenomenon occur based on the generation and/or evaluation of theories.
- They can generate or evaluate theories about how or why phenomena occur.

The PRISMA 2020 [1] methodology, although mainly developed and used in the medical and clinical sciences, could be also applied in engineering and education, as it provides guidance in methodologies to identify, select, appraise and synthesize the available literature. This document presents the protocol adopted to conduct a systematic literature review with the aim of exploring how the Architecture, Engineering, Construction, Management, Operation, and Conservation (AECMO&C) industry can adapt and be better prepared to embrace novel Industry 5.0 principles and enabling technologies, ultimately resulting in enhanced conservation practices for the built cultural heritage environment. It follows the checklist provided by PRISMA and guidelines of the PRISMA-P Explanation and Elaboration [2].

1.2 Protocol

The recommended items to address in a systematic review protocol according to the PRISMA-P methodology [3, 4] are presented in Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 1. Administrative information

Title:	
Identification	Industry 5.0 Concepts and Enabling Technologies, Towards an Enhanced Conservation Practice: Systematic Literature Review Protocol
Update	-
Registration:	This protocol has been registered in the OSF Registries website (https://osf.io/registries) under the Generalized Systematic Review Registration Form [5] on 24/02/2024. Its registration number is GPY6B [6].
Authors:	
Contact	Alejandro Jiménez Ríos ^{1,*} , Margarita L. Petrou ² , Rafael Ramirez ³ , Vagelis Plevris ⁴ and Maria Nogal ⁵
	¹ Department of Built Environment, Oslo Metropolitan University, P.O. Box 4, St. Olavs plass, NO-0130, Oslo, Norway. alejand@oslomet.no
	² Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, University of Cyprus, P.O. Box 20537, 1678, Nicosia, Cyprus. mpetro03@ucy.ac.cy
	³ Department of Civil Engineering, ISE, ARISE, University of Minho, Campus de Azurém s/n, 4800-058 Guimarães, Portugal. rramirez@civil.uminho.pt
	⁴ Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Qatar University, P.O. Box 2713, Doha, Qatar. vplevris@qu.edu.qa
	⁵ Materials, Mechanics, Management and Design Department, Delft University of Technology, 2628 CN, Delft, The Netherlands. m.nogal@tudelft.nl
	*Corresponding author

Contributions	Guarantor: AJR. Conceptualization: AJR. Investigation: AJR, MLP, RR. Methodology: AJR, MLP, RR. Project Administration: AJR, VP, MN. Resources: AJR, VP, MN. Supervision: VP, MN. Writing – original draft preparation: AJR, MP, RR. Writing – review and editing: AJR, VP, MN.
Amendments	In the event of protocol amendments, the date of each amendment will be accompanied by a description of the change and the rationale. See Annex A.
Support:	
Sources	This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 101066739. Support was also provided by the International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property (ICCROM) by granting access to ICCROM extensive bibliographic resources during the time this work was conducted to AJR within the context of a prestigious ICCROM Fellowship.
Sponsor Role of sponsor/funder	The European Union funded this research. The funder is not involved in any other aspect of the project and will have no input on the interpretation or publication of the study results.

Table 2. Introduction.

Rationale:	<p>Built cultural heritage refers to man-made structures, buildings, landmarks, and spaces with historical, architectural, artistic, cultural, or social significance [7]. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) promotes worldwide cultural equality and heritage conservation. By adopting the World Heritage Convention (WHC) in 1972, Member States of UNESCO are responsible for identifying, protecting, conserving, and presenting the world’s heritage [8]. Unfortunately, these invaluable assets are vulnerable to different socio-economic and natural hazards, especially in the face of climate change and its effects [9]. The United Nations (UN) recognizes in Target 11.4 of the Sustainability Development Goals (SDG) that safeguarding cultural heritage contributes to making cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable [10]. Thus, endeavors to preserve the built cultural heritage environment are both required and desired [11].</p> <p>Previous work indicates that a suitable Industry 4.0 digital twin framework for built cultural heritage assets would be primarily based on an As-Is Historical Asset Information Model (AI-HAIM) [12]. This AI-HAIM must contain interoperable data, geometry, finite element, and data-driven modules (“digital asset”) and be linked to its real-world counterpart through a multi-metric asset health monitoring system. That system should continuously produce data on the asset’s structural, environmental, and operational conditions (“physical asset”). Major challenges in creating Industry 4.0 digital twins include: i) lack of interoperability among different software used in the digital twin model generation; ii) unclear guidelines for creating macro-digital twins integrating individual asset models, and iii) absence of Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) benchmark databases suitable for digital twin prototyping development and validation [13, 14].</p> <p>While the vision of Industry 4.0 has driven digitalization and increased productivity, it has been deemed inadequate to achieve European goals by 2030 [15]. Thus, a novel Industry 5.0 paradigm has emerged. Industry 5.0 is mainly based on three foundational ideas: i) human-centrism, ii) resilience, and iii) sustainability. The recognized enabling technologies of this new transformative vision include: a) Individualized human-machine-interaction, b) bio-inspired technologies and smart materials, c) digital twins and simulation, d) data transmission, storage, and analysis technologies, e) artificial intelligence, and f) technologies for efficiency, renewables, storage, and autonomy [16].</p>
Objectives:	<p>The objective of this systematic literature review is to collect and synthesize state-of-the-art knowledge and information, identify how Industry 5.0 concepts and enabling technologies can contribute to the improvement of built cultural heritage conservation practices, identify current gaps, and highlight future potential developments and opportunities in the field. To this end, the proposed systematic review will answer the following question:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How can the architecture, engineering, construction, management, operation, and conservation (AECMO&C) industry adapt and be better prepared to embrace novel Industry 5.0 concepts ultimately leading to enhanced practices in built cultural heritage conservation?

Table 3. Methods.

Eligibility criteria:	<p>Peer reviewed records published as Articles, Conference Paper, Book Chapters, or Review in Journals, Conference Proceedings, Books, or Book Series within the subject areas of Computer Science, Engineering, Business Management and Accounting, Decision Sciences, Social Sciences, Economics Econometrics and Finance, Energy, Environmental Science, Materials Science, Arts and Humanities, and Multidisciplinary, from 2020 up to 2024, written in English, and containing the following keywords of interest (and similar terms, namely: human-centrism and human-centric, etc.) as part of the record's title, abstract, or keywords, will be initially included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industry 5.0. • Principles: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Human-Centrism. ○ Resilience. ○ Sustainability. • Enabling Technologies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Human-centric solutions. ○ Human-machine-interaction. ○ Bio-inspired technologies. ○ Smart materials. ○ Digital twins. ○ Cyber safe data. ○ Artificial intelligence. ○ Energy efficiency. ○ Trustworthy autonomy. <p>In combination with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Built Cultural Heritage Environment. • Conservation.
Information sources:	See [17].
Search strategy:	See [17]
Study records:	
Data management	See [17].
Selection process	<p>The selection process will follow the PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for systematic reviews [1].</p> <p>All remaining records after deduplication will be screened by two independent reviewers based on title, abstract and keywords. Disagreements on the selection process would be resolved by a third reviewer who will ultimately decide on the selection or rejection of the record.</p> <p>All records remaining from the screening process will be sought for retrieval. Found records will be assessed for eligibility based on the entire content.</p>
Data collection process	Data will be collected from the included records through a qualitative summary approach.
Data items:	The data items of interest would be the information related to the three principles (human-centrism, resilience, sustainability) and enabling technologies (human-machine-interaction, bio-inspired technologies and smart materials, digital twins and simulation, data transmission, storage, and analysis technologies, artificial intelligence, and energy efficiency and trustworthy autonomy) of Industry 5.0 applied within a built cultural heritage conservation context.
Outcomes and prioritization:	<p>The main outcomes of the review will be the qualitative data related to the exploration, preparedness, adoption, or implementation measurements related to Industry 5.0 principles and enabling technologies within a built cultural heritage conservation context.</p> <p>Secondary outcomes would be related to the specifics and characteristics of the built cultural heritage assets where such principles and enabling technologies have been applied, when such information is provided within the included records.</p>
Risk of bias in individual studies:	The risk of bias and quality of individual studies will be assessed based on the prior experience and background knowledge of the authors of the review working on similar reviews on the past.
Data synthesis:	Both a bibliometric analysis and a narrative synthesis will be performed.

The approaches for the bibliometric analysis will be a performance analysis and a science mapping. The performance analysis will be presented in terms of publications per year, most cited authors, most cited records, documents per country, keyword occurrence, and most used source for publication. On the other hand, the science mapping will analyze the co-authorship relationships in terms of authors and countries, as well as the co-occurrence relationships between keywords (both author and index keywords).

The information of the included records will be qualitatively summarized in a narrative synthesis as the findings are characterized by heterogeneity.

Meta-bias(es):	No meta-bias assessment is planned for the proposed systematic review.
Confidence in cumulative evidence:	No confidence assessment plan will be used for the proposed systematic review. This is based in the fact that no universally accepted methodology is available for the grading of reviewing in the AECMO&C field.

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Annex A

Table 4. History of changes.

Version	Publication date	Change
1.0	26/03/2024	Initial version.

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